

BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology

Industrial Training Report On HAMS Garments LTD. Dakkhin Vangnahati Sreepur, Gazipur

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This internship report submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of B.Sc. in Textile Engineering department (TE) in the faculty of Textile Engineering of BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology (BUFT).

Department of Textile Engineering
BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology
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On
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March 2023

Letter of Transmittal

12th March, 2023

Mr. Faisal Ahmed

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Nishatnagar, Dhaka

Subject: Submission of Internship Report.

Dear Sir,

We are extremely indebted for your tremendous support and guidance throughout our long journey at "BGMEA University of Fashion and technology" and internship period. Being working with you, we have earned valuable knowledge and were inspired by your innovativeness, which helped enrich our experience to a greater extent. An internship report on " HAMS Garments Ltd." is submitted to you for the partial fulfillment of the Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering Degree.

During our internship period, we have trained in all departments of HAMS Garments Ltd.; we made sincere efforts to study related materials, observe operations performed in Knitting, Dyeing(fabric), Garments, Washing which are the sources of collected data to prepare the present report on Wet Processing Technology.

We have to make this report as comprehensive as possible within the time limit. But there may be some mistakes due to various limitations. For this reason, we beg your sympathetic consideration. Finally, we pray for your blessing for our successful engineering career.

Thank you

Yours Faithfully

Md. Jahidul Islam (ID: 191-361-801)

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BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology

Declaration

It is hereby declared that, the internship report over **HAMS Garments LTD** is my own original work while completing degree at **BGMEA University of Fashion and technology**.

The report does not contain material previously published or written by a third party, except where this is appropriately cited through full and accurate referencing. The report does not contain material which has been accepted, or submitted, for any other degree or diploma at a university or other institution. I have acknowledged all main sources of help.

I also want to declare that this report was prepared solely for academic purposes and that no confidential information about the industry was disclosed in this report; and that I was instructed to prepare this report by my supervisor, MR. Faisal Ahmed.

Board of Examiners

Name

Signature

1. **Supervisor:** MR. Faisal Ahmed.

2. **Examiner 1:**

3. **Examiner 2:**

Acknowledgement

Firstly, I would like to thank to Almighty Allah who has given the opportunity to finish this three-month long-time training program and report. Secondly, I would like to thank those people who co-operate me to finish this report more effectively. For their guide line, cooperation also helped me too much to complete this report effectively. I would like to thank my industrial supervisor **Md. Faisal Ahmed (Pavel)** for his guidelines & suggestions which direct me how to complete this training successfully. He helped me to collect effective information from different departments within this short time.

And I would like to thank also my academic supervisor **Mr. Faisal Ahmed** who has checked my internship report with essential correction. He has advised the way of successful completion of training. I also thank to **Mr. Reaz Uddin**, Sr.Manager (Knitting), **Mr. Shovon**, Manager (Dyeing), **Md. Shadath Hasan**, DGM (Merchandising), for giving me inspiration & advise as well as information & current strategy of overall. Thanks goes to all Engineers, officers, technicians, employees, stuffs, all section in-charges for their cordial behavior and help.

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Finally, I want to thank the authority of HAMS Group who gave me the opportunity to complete my industrial attachment here and grateful to the authority of BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology for designing such an effective course including industrial training program.

Executive Summary

HAMS Group is a 100% export oriented leading garments industry starts journey in 2001 with 2 sewing lines and total of 350 workforces at Sreepur area in Gazipur city in Bangladesh. Now it's quite 12,000 workforces with 153 sewing lines within different project of HAMS Group in Gazipur. It expands business into knit, woven, and lingerie products.

The garment manufacturing industry continues to remain the major promoter of the Bangladesh economy even in 2022 with more promising future in the times ahead. One can see drastic changes in the industry's practices that have taken place in last one decade – all thanks to the incredible efforts made by the progressive groups in the country that have taken the commitment on themselves to innovate processes and products in order to align themselves to the country's goal of achieving US \$ 100 billion export turnover by 2030.

It's a known fact that Hams Group has one of the largest washing plants in Bangladesh that's named – Hams Washing & Dyeing Ltd., which was started 24 years ago and has now been upgraded to Dhaka Garments & Washing Ltd. It was in 2010 when the company realized the need of venturing into garment manufacturing business and started Hams Garments Ltd., and since then, the knitwear project has seen an unprecedented growth in the last 12 years as almost all big and renowned brands are currently working with Hams Group as buyers.

Not just knits, the group is strengthening its woven division too. The demand in the global apparel market for woven apparel products was massive in pre-pandemic time which is regaining its momentum after a temporary shortfall during pandemic. The factory was started in 2019 and currently has 32 sewing lines operational that collectively produce 850,000 pieces per month.

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CHAPTER 1: PROJECT DESCRIPTION

1.1 Introduction

RMG (Ready Made Garment) is very important and helpful for Bangladesh. Bangladesh has emerged as key player in Ready Made Garment since 1978. Textile and clothing for about 85% export income for Bangladesh out of which 75% comes from apparel sector which covers the major product knit and woven shirt, blouses, trouser, skirt, shorts, jacket, sweater sportswear and many more casual and fashionable outfit. This sector at present employs approximately 1.5 million plus worker mostly female who are comes from under privileged social class.

This part explains the Purpose, Scope and Limitation. It also gives an introduction to the Company, HAMS Group, including its background, Company Profile, research goals and university partnerships. This part also summarizes the background information of the 'Industrial Training Report' as well as the students' responsibilities.

1.2 Objectives of Industrial Training

- To enhance our university learning experience through involvement in industrial and commercial field, thus enabling us to relate theoretical concepts with practical situation.
- To develop and enhance our professional awareness and communication skill
- To study the present market condition of RMG product, growth, achievement, competition.
- To develop skills and techniques directly applicable to our careers.
- To build strength, teamwork spirit, and self-confidence.
- To find out the ways to improve the loop hole for doing better performance of HAMS Garments Ltd.
- To get a brief knowledge about different types of machinery, equipment and overall activities of an Industry.

1.3 Methodology of the Report

The report is based on both primary and secondary data. But maximum data used in this report are collected from secondary sources. Exact sources of the secondary sources will be mentioned. Thus, the report is basically qualitative in nature.

However, primarily I gathered data directly from employees of the firms, and I gathered primary data for this report by using the approach outlined below: Having a face-to-face conversation about a pertinent topic. While working at the company, I observed my coworkers directly.

Secondarily, I gathered data from the Official Website of HAMS, the site has a relevant article. Various public documents are also available.

1.4 About HAMS Group.

Figure 1.1: HAMS Group Fabric & RMG Unit

HAMS Group is established in 1994 and remained one of the leading vertical textile manufacturers in the country to date. With an indelible commitment - employing highly skilled textile professionals, equipped with latest machinery and providing outstanding working conditions for all our employees. We always believed in creating the best Product that considered as value for money at the consumer's end.

For around 25 years, they continuously focus on current trends, including customer needs and end-user demands into the manufacturing process of high-quality knit and apparel, and establishing themselves as the leading provider of knit clothing for the international market.

1.5 Company Profile

Company name	HAMS Group
Type	100% export oriented knit garments factory
Name of Owner	Engr. Shafiqur Rahman
Year of Foundation	1994
Company Logo	
Corporate office address	House # 01, Road # 06, Block # F, Niketon, Gulshan-1, Dhaka-1212
Fabric, RMG Unit	Dakkhin Vangnahati, Boiragirchala, Sreepure, Gazipure- 1740
Contact no	9897847
E-mail	info@hams.com.bd
Website	www.hams.com.bd
Business field	All categories of Men's, Women's
No of Employees	15000+

Table 1.1: Company profile

Certificates and Awards:

Organic Content Standard (OCS), Organic Blended Content Standard (OBCS), Recycled Claim Standard (RCS), Supplier Ethical Data Exchange (SEDEX), Better Cotton Initiative (BCI), Amfori (BSCI), ACCORD, Zero Discharge of Hazardous Chemicals (ZDHC).

1.6 Sister concerns of HAMS Group

1. HAMS Garments Ltd.

HAMS Garments Ltd. Operates in its own building in Dakkhin Vangnahati, Boiragirchala, Sreepure, Gazipure- 1740, Dhaka with its 20 years of knowledge and experience in readymade garments industry. They offer advantages and efficiencies to their customer with quality garment in timely manner. While achieving their high quality of work they are following with all local laws, regulation, child labor policy, human right policies and environmental practices.

2. DHAKA Garments &Washing Ltd.

Md. Shafiqur Rahman, founder & managing director of this company, is a textile engineer himself who provided service for eighteen years in garments washing and dyeing sector. In September 1998 with five local made garments washing and dyeing machine he launched Dhaka Garments & Washing Ltd. The commitment was “TO MAINTAIN QUALITY AND TO DELIVER TIMELY” and still strongly believes it.

Within five years the industry earned good reputation in garments washing & dyeing sector.

Now HAMS WASHING & DYEING LTD. is one of the leading garments washing & dyeing industry in Bangladesh.

The industry is now equipped with modern washing & dyeing machines. The total numbers of machine are five times than the initial set up.

3. HAMS Fashion Ltd.

Hams fashion ltd is a part of HAMS group. It's situated in South Vangnahati, Sreepur, Gazipur. The factory size is large but the factory roads should be improved. HAMS Fashion ltd. Is mainly printing factory.

4. Victoria Intimate Ltd

It establishing in 2019 Is One of The Pioneers in The Textile Sector. Over the course of time, it has become a one-stop solution for all kinds of fabric, embellishment, washing & garments manufacturing. This will be a 60-line hi-tech project & the monthly production capacity will be 2.5M Pcs. At present they have 15 sewing lines set up with a monthly capacity of 0.6M Pcs.

1.7 Organogram of HAMS Group (Production)

Chart 1.1: Organogram of HAMS Group (Production)

1.8 Business Partners

HAMS Group works with worldwide leading brands in apparel sector.

Buyers Name	Country	Logo
M&S (Marks & Spencer)	UK	
H&M (Hennes & Mauritz)	Sweden	
C&A	Belgium	
Next	England	
Kmart	US	
New look	UK	
s.Oliver	Germany	

Table 1.2: Business partners

1.9 Different Departments and Sections of HAMS Group

1. Administration
2. Accounts, HR & Compliance
3. Marketing & Merchandising
4. Computer Aided Design (CAD)
5. Sampling Department
6. Quality Assurance Department
7. Research & Development (R&D)
8. Knitting Department
9. Cutting Department
10. Printing Department & Embroidery Department
11. Sewing Department
12. IE Department
13. Quality Control Department
14. Finishing Department
15. Planning Department
16. Commercial Department
17. Maintenance Department

1.10 Production Phases (Shifting System)

- General Shift: Three Shift
 1. 06.00 AM – 02.00PM
 2. 02.00 PM – 10.00 PM
 3. 10.00 PM – 06.00 AM
- Day Shift: 08.00 AM - 08.00 PM (Including 3 hours Over Time)

CHAPTER 2: KNITTING SECTION

2.1 Knitting

Knitting is the interlocking of one or more yarns through a series of loops. The length wise columns of stitches, corresponding to the warp in woven cloth, are called Wales; the cross wise rows of stitches, corresponding to the filling in woven cloth, are called Courses, Filling Knits (Weft Knits) are those fabrics in which the courser composed of a single strand of yarn, while warp knits are those in which the Wales are composed of single strand of yarn. Gauge corresponds to the yarn in a woven fabric, and is defined as the number if needles of yarns in half inches of cloth. The higher the gauge, the more compact and finer is the cloth.

2.2 Layout of knitting section

Figure 2.1: Knitting section layout

2.3 Specification of Knitting machine (knitting section)

No	Machine Type	M/C Dia	M/C Gauge	M/C Feeder	Quantity
01	Engineering Stripe Rib Machine	30	18	44	1
02	Rib Interlock Machine	34	18	72	1
03	Rib Interlock Machine	36	18	72	1
04	Rib Interlock Machine	40	18	80	1
05	Rib Interlock Machine	42	18	84	1
06	Single Jersey Machine	24	24	72	1
07	Single Jersey Machine	26	24	78	2 (7&8)
08	Single Jersey Machine	28	24	84	1
09	Single Jersey Machine	28	28	84	1
10	Single Jersey Machine	30	24	90	2 (11&12)
11	Single Jersey Machine	38	24	114	2 (13&14)
12	Single Jersey Machine	42	24	126	2 (15&16)
13	Engineering Stripe Single Jersey	30	24	42	2 (17&18)
14	Collar-Cuff (Semi-jacquard)	80	14	06	4 (1-4)
Total No of Machine					22

Table 2.1: Knitting Machine.

M/C No	Model	Needle	Origin	Brand
Machine: 1	KSCS/4,6-U	3384	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 2	KD2.5B	3840	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 3	KD2.5B	4068	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 4	KD2.5B	4512	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 5	KD2.5B	4740	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 6	KS3B	1800	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 7&8	KS3B	1968	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 9&10	KS3B	2112	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 11&12	KS3B	2256	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 13&14	KS3B	2868	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 15&16	KS3B	3168	Taiwan	Pailung
Machine: 17&18	KSCS/4,6-U	2256	Taiwan	Pailung

Table 2.2: Knitting Machine Specifications

Total Machine: 22

Rib Interlock Machine: 4

Engineering Stripe Single Jersey: 2

Engineering Stripe Rib: 1

Single Jersey: 11

Flat Bed (Semi-jacquard): 4

Figure 2.2: Knitting Floor

Figure 2.3: Flat Bed (Semi-jacquard)

Figure 2.4: Single Jersey Machine

Figure 2.5: Engineering Stripe Rib Machine

2.4 Knitting process Flowchart

Chart 2.1: Flow chart of Knitting Process

2.5 Which Fabrics are produced

HAMS Group produces different types of knit fabrics –

1. Single jersey
2. Rib
3. Interlock
4. Terry
5. Fleece
6. Pique

7. Lacoste (single, double)
8. Auto Stripe
9. Engineering Stripe
10. Lycra plated

2.6 Different parts of Circular Knitting Machine

Creel: Creel is used to place the cone.

Cone holder: Yarn cone placed for feeding the yarn easily.

Aluminum tube: Yarn passed.

MPF Device: (Memminger positive feed) It received yarn from tube and gives a Positive feed from tube and gives a positive feed of yarn to the needle.

Lycra attachment Device: Feed the Lycra yarn.

Yarn Guide: Yarn Received from MPF.

Feeder guide: It received yarn from yarn guide.

Feeder: Feeder is used to feed the yarn.

Needle: Create loop.

Tensioning device: Tensioning device is used to give proper tension to the yarn.

VDQ pulley: VDQ pulley is used to control the GSM by controlling the stitch length.

Pulley belt: Gives motion.

Guide: Guide is used to guide the yarn.

Cam: Control the motion.

Cam box: Holds Cam, and cam arranged horizontally in this box.

M/C Body: It hold the machine

Base plate: It hold the cylinder.

Air gun: It blow Air.

Adjustable fan: It remove Dust and help to cool the needle.

Lubrication tube: Supplies lubricant.

Gate: It helps covered the fabric.

Sensor: Sensor is used to seen & the machine stops when any problem occurs.

Spreader: Spreader is used to spread the knitted fabric before take up roller.

Take up roller: Take up roller is used to take up the fabric.

Motion roller: It pull the fabric and grip also take fabric down.

<u>MPF Parts</u>	<u>Cam</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Winding wheel• Driven pulley• Sensor IV.• Top stopper, bottom stopper• Yarn tensioner	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Knit Cam• Miss Cam• Tuck Cam

Table 2.3: MPF & Cam

2.7 Considerable points to produce Knitted Fabric

When a buyer orders for fabric then they mention some points related to production and quality.

Before production of knitted fabric, these factors are needed to consider –

- Type of Fabric or design of Fabric
- Finished G.S.M.
- Yarn count
- Types of yarn (combed or carded) diameter of the fabric.
- Stitch length Color depth.

2.8 Some points to maintain High Quality Fabrics

- Brought good quality yarn.
- Machines are oiled and greased accordingly.
- G.S.M, Stitch length, Tensions are controlled accurately.
- Machines are cleaned every shift and servicing is done after a month.
- Grey Fabrics are checked by 4-point grading system

2.9 Four Point system:

<p># 4 Point system:</p> <p>0-3" = 1 Point</p> <p>>3-6" = 2 Point</p> <p>>6-9" = 3 Point</p> <p>> 9" = 4 Point Hole</p>	<p>Acceptable Calculation:</p> <p>Up to 20 Point = A</p> <p>Up to 20 Point = B</p> <p>Up to 20 Point = C</p> <p>Up to 20 Point = Reject</p>
--	---

Table 2.4: Four Point system

2.10 Fabric Relaxation Time

Types of Fabric	Relaxation Time
Cotton fabric	24 hours
Lycra fabric	36 hours
Pique/ Lacoste fabric	36 hours
Polyester fabric	36 hours
Spandex fabric	36 hours
Cotton + Polyester fabric	24 hours

Table 2.5: Fabric relaxation time

2.11 Production Parameter

- Machine Diameter
- Machine rpm (revolution per minute)
- No. of feeds or feeders in use
- Machine Gauge
- Count of yarn
- Required time (M/C running time)
- Machine running efficiency

2.12 Faults and their Causes & Remedies in Knitting

2.12.1 Hole Mark Causes:

- Holes are the results of yarn breakage or yarn cracks.
- During loop formation the yarn breaks in the rejoin of the needle hook.
- If the yarn count is not correct on regarding structure, gauge, course and density.
- Badly knot or splicing.
- Yarn feeder badly set.

Remedies:

- Yarn strength must be sufficient to withstand the stretch as well as uniform.
- Use proper count of yarn.
- Correctly set of yarn feeder.
- Knot should be given properly.

2.12.2 Needle Mark Causes:

- When a needle breaks down then needle mark comes along the fabrics.
- If a needle or needle hook is slightly bended then needle mark comes on the fabrics.

Remedies:

- Needle should be straight as well as from broken latch.
- Bent needle should be changed.

2.12.3 Drop stitch Causes:

- Defective needle.
- If yarn is not properly fed during loop formation i.e. not properly laid on to the needle hook.
- Take-down mechanism too loose.
- Insufficient yarn tension.
- Badly set yarn feeder.

Remedies:

- Needle should be straight & well.

- Proper feeding of yarn during loop formation.
- Correct take up of the fabric & correct fabric tension.
- Yarn tension should be perfect.

2.12.4 Oil stitch

Causes: When oil lick through the needle trick then it passes on the fabrics and make a line.

Remedies: Ensure that oil does not pass on the fabrics.

2.12.5 Pin hole

Causes: Due to break down or bend of the latch, pin hole may come in the fabric.

Remedies: Change the needle

2.12.6 Fly dusts

Causes: In knitting section too, much lint is flying that are created from yarn due to low twist as well as yarn friction. This lint may adhere or attaches to the fabric surface tightly during knit fabric production.

Remedies:

- Blowing air for cleaning and different parts after a certain period of time.
- By cleaning the floor continuously.
- By using ducting system for cleaning too much lint in the floor.
- Over all ensure that lint does not attach to the fabric.

2.12.7 Yarn Contamination

Causes:

- If yarn contains foreign fiber, then it remains in the fabric even after finishing,
- If lot, count mixing occurs.

Remedies:

- By avoiding lot, count mixing.
- Fault less spinning.

2.12.8 Lycra out and tension variation of Lycra

Causes: Breakage of Lycra yarn & uneven tension of Lycra.

Remedies:

- To maintain uniform tension

2.12.9 Yarn miss

Causes: Yarn breakage due to any reason and not pass through the yarn guide. It may be occurred for tension variation.

Remedies:

- Yarn guide and tensioner must be used.

2.12.10 Lycra and cotton mixed

Causes: Lycra yarn twisted with cotton yarn.

Remedies:

- Correct the lycra path.
- Clear the yarn guide.

2.13 Fabric inspection Machine

Figure 2.6: Fabric inspection Machine

2.14 Fabric GSM

Fabric GSM means the weight in gram per square meter. GSM indicates the fabric weight. If the fabric GSM is higher than the fabric is coarser or thicker. Fabric GSM is checked by GSM cutter m/c. which area one parts of 100 of one square meter. Fabric GSM means weight in gm of one square meter.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Area} &= 100 \times 100 \text{ cm}^2 \\ &= 10,000 \text{ cm}^2\end{aligned}$$

GSM cutter area = 100 cm², which is one part of Area of one square meter.

GSM Calculation:

C is a scale which is used for calculation the GSM of a fabric. The dia of the circle is 11.28 cm.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Area of the Scale is} &= \pi r^2 \\ &= 3.14 \times (11.28 \div 2)^2 \\ &= 100 \text{ cm}^2\end{aligned}$$

GSM = Wt of 100 cm² fabric in centigram (×100) gm.

$$\begin{aligned}&= (0.150 \times 100) \text{ gm} \\ &= 150 \text{ gm.}\end{aligned}$$

2.15 Methods of increasing Knitting Production

- 1. By increasing m/c speed:** Higher the m/c speed faster the movement of needle and ultimately production will be increased. But it has to make sure that excess tension is not imposed on yarn because of this high speed.
- 2. By increasing the number of feeders:** If the number of feeders is increased in the circumference of cylinder, then the number of courses will be increased in one revolution at a time.
- 3. By using machine of higher gauge:** The more the machine gauge, the more the production is. So, by using machine of higher gauge production can be increased.

4. By imposing automation in the m/c: Quick starting & stopping for efficient driving system, Automatic m/c lubrication system for smoother operation, Photo electric fabric fault detector.

CHAPTER 3: DYEING

3.1 Dyeing

Dyeing is the process of adding color to textile products like fibers, yarns, and fabrics through a dye (color). Dyeing can be done at any stage of the manufacturing of textile- fiber, yarn, fabric or a finished textile product including garments and apparels.

Dyeing is the application of dyes or pigments on textile materials such as fibers, yarns, and fabrics with the goal of achieving color with desired color fastness. Dyeing is normally done in a special solution containing dyes and particular chemical material.

3.2 Dyeing department

- 60 thousand Sq. Ft
- 20,000 kgs per day dyeing production
- 30,000 kgs per day finishing production
- 27 sets of Dyeing machines
- Capacity from 10 kgs to 1250 kgs
- 12 sets of Finishing machines
- Both open and tube finishing facility
- 3 Stenter of 8 chambers and 1 relax dryer
- Open and tube compactor.
- Brushing facility

Future Expansion

- Dyeing: 20 sets of new dyeing mc will be added by 2020~21
- 20~25 Ton additional capacity
- MC capacity will be 8 kgs to 1500 kgs
- Finishing will be equipped with Stenter, Compacting, Sanforizing, Relax dryer, Singeing, Brushing, Suedeing, Shearing.

3.4.2 Function and Purpose of Batch Section

- To receive the grey fabric roll from knitting section or other source.
- Turn the grey fabric if require.
- To prepare the batch of fabric for dyeing according to the following criteria.
 - Order sheet (Received from buyer)
 - Dyeing shade (color or white, light or dark)
 - Machine capacity
 - Machine available
 - Type of fabrics (100% cotton, PE, PC, CVC)
 - Emergency
- To send the grey fabric to the dyeing floor with batch card.
- To keep records for every previous dyeing.

3.4.3 Proper batching criteria

- To use maximum capacity of existing dyeing m/c.
- To minimize the washing time or preparation time & m/c stoppage time.
- To keep the no. of batch as less as possible for same shade.
- To use a particular m/c for dyeing same shade

3.4.4 Batch Management (Type of Batch)

01). Solid Batch 02). Ratio Batch

Solid Batch: In solid batch all sample are same size, same diameter, same GSM, same fabric. For example; GSM is 160, diameter is 60", and fabric type is single jersey.

Ratio Batch: In ratio batch sample are different size, different diameter, different GSM, different fabric. For example; GSM are 160; 180; 200; diameters are (45"; 50"; 56"; 60"), fabric type is single jersey; (1*1) rib; (2*2) rib; (1*1) interlock, color sizes are (38*9; 40*9; 42*9; 45*9), cuff size are (38*3; 39*3; 40*3; 42.5*3),

Considerable point: Batch selection depends on Fabric GSM.

3.5 Lab Section

At first dyeing is performed in dyeing laboratory and then starting for bulk production. A lot of work is done in the dyeing laboratory. In the dyeing lab, lab dip or sample is developed by the dyeing master. Lab dip plays an important role in shade matching & this is an important task before bulk production. In HAMS Garments Ltd under Hams Group there have both Physical testing lab & Chemical testing lab. Its buyer nominated lab.

3.5.1 Laboratory flow chart for organic process:

Chart 3.2: Laboratory flow chart for organic process

3.5.2 Development of Lab Dip:

Chart 3.3: Flow chart of Lab Dip Development

3.5.3 Finished Fabric Quality Tests in Lab

- Color Fastness to Washing
- Color Fastness to Water
- Color Fastness to Light
- Color Fastness to Perspiration
- Color Fastness to Saliva
- Color Fastness to Rubbing (Dry & Wet)
- Dimensional Stability to Wash
- Spirality Test
- Bursting Strength
- Fabric pH
- Pilling Test

3.5.4 Machine Specification of Dyeing Lab

Machine Name	Brand	Origin	Purpose
Crock Master	James H Heal	UK	Color Fastness to Rubbing
Warp Reel	FYI	China	Yarn Count Check
TPI Tester	Gester	China	Yarn Twist Tester

Machine Name	Brand	Origin	Purpose
Pilling Tester	James H Heal	UK	Pilling & Snagging Tester
Martindale	James H Heal	UK	Pilling Tester
Burst Tester	James H Heal	UK	Bursting Strength Tester
Yarn Examine	Gester	China	Yarn Evenness Check
Universal Strength	James H Heal	UK	Tensile Strength, Seam Sleafage

Table 3.1: Machine Specification of Dyeing Lab

3.6 Specification of Sample Dyeing Machine (Dyeing Section)

Machine No.	Brand	Origin	Capacity	Nozzle	Quantity
01	Dilmenler	Turkey	25 kg	1	1
02	Dilmenler	Turkey	50 kg	1	1
03 & 04	Fong's	Hong Kong	30 kg	1	2
05	Fong's	Hong Kong	50 kg	1	1
19 & 20	Fong's	Hong Kong	10 kg	1	2
21-24	Sclavos	Greece	50 kg	1	4
Total Sample Dyeing Machine				11	

Table 3.2: Specification of Sample Dyeing Machine

Figure 3.2: Sample Dyeing Machine

3.7 Specification of Bulk Dyeing Machine

Machine No.	Brand	Origin	Capacity	Temp.	Nozzle
06	Fong's	Hong Kong	120 kg	140	1
07	Fong's	Hong Kong	280 kg	145	1
08	Fong's	Hong Kong	500 kg	140	2
09	Fong's	Hong Kong	800 kg	140	4
10	Canler	Turkey	750 kg	135	3
11	Canler	Turkey	1250 kg	140	5
12	Fong's	Hong Kong	200 kg	140	1
13	Fong's	Hong Kong	750 kg	140	3
14	Fong's	Hong Kong	800 kg	145	4
15	Dilmenler	Turkey	250 kg	145	1
16	Dilmenler	Turkey	1000 kg	145	4
17	Sclavos	Greece	980 kg	145	4
18	Dilmenler	Turkey	450 kg	130	3
26	Sclavos	Greece	1250	145	4

Table 3.3: Specification of Bulk Dyeing Machine

Figure 3.3: Bulk Dyeing Machine

3.8 Chemical Used in Dyeing Section

Functional Name	Chemicals Name
General Chemical	Soda Ash
	Caustic
	Hydrogen Peroxide
	Hydrose
	Contripon S
Acid	Sulphuric Acid
	Acetic Acid
	Formic Acid
	Oxalic Acid
Cationic Softener	Softener S400
	Softener FF-CWS

Functional Name	Chemicals Name
Non-ionic softener	Noamin WHI/z-2021
	Dovosil Micro N 66
Anti-creasing Agent	Infacream ACA
	Persotex AFC
	Lubrimax TL-E
	Albafluid C
Fixing Agent	Fixing Agent HF-01
	Fixing Agent HF-08
	Asufix MF-R
PH-Buffer	Albatex AB-45
Soaping Agent	Exoline 3027
	Oxinol CNW
Sequestering Agent	Invatex CS
	Sequestering 710
	Toxal TAC
Levelling	Croscolor SLR New
	Croscolor ADM
Enzyme	BIO j-1085
	Power finish
	Mazyme ECO
Stabilizer	Clarite CBB
GSM Improver	Alkasoft-WIA
Anti-Back Staining	Crosden LPD
Shade Definer	Protelan LGA

Table 3.4: Chemicals Used in Dyeing Section

3.9 Flow Chart of Fabric Dyeing

Chart 3.4: Flow Chart of Fabric Dyeing

3.10 Dyeing Parameter

3.10.1 PH Check during Wet Processing:

Bleaching bath pH	10.5 – 11
Neutralization / after bleaching pH	5.5 – 6.5
Initial dye bath pH	5.5 – 6.5
After salt addition pH	6.5 – 7.5
After alkali addition pH	10.5 – 11.2
After dyeing pH	5.0 – 6.0
Fixation bath pH	4.5 – 5.5
Softener bath PH	4.0 -5.0 (for color) / 5.5 – 6.0 (for white)

3.10.2 Fixation Time:

For light shade	30 – 40 min
For medium shade	45 – 50 min
For deep shade	50 – 60 min

3.10.3 M: L ratio: 1:6 – 1:10

3.10.4 The amount of Glauber salt and Soda ash on the basic shade percentage:

60°C Soda Ash (L: R=1:10)

Dyes	<0.1	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	>7.0
Glauber Salt(g/l)	30	30	50	50	60	80	80	80
Soda Ash (g/l)	3.0	5.0	10.0	12.0	15.0	20.0	20.0	20.0

80°C Soda Ash (L: R=1:10)

Dyes	<0.1	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	>7.0
Glauber Salt(g/l)	10	30	30	40	50	50	50	50
Soda Ash (g/l)	3.0	3.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	10.0	10.0	10.0

3.11 Dyeing Recipe & Process:

Recipe for 100% Cotton Single Jersey Fabric:

Machine No.	27	Date	25-01-2023
Fabric Type	100% CTN	GSM	180
Fabric weight	421 kg	M:L	1:6
Color	Gardenia Solid	Total Liquor	2526 Ltr.

Function	Dosing (Ratio)	Quantity	Remark
Pre-Treatment (Scouring & Bleaching)			
Detergent	0.40%	1.014 kg	98°C × 60 min.
Sequestering agent	0.30%	0.757 kg	
Anti-creasing agent	0.01%	0.025 kg	
Caustic soda	1.8%	4.546 kg	

Function	Dosing (Ratio)	Quantity	Remark
Pre-Treatment (Scouring & Bleaching)			
Stabilizer	0.30%	0.757 kg	98°C × 60 min.
Peroxide	3%	7.578 kg	
Neutralization & peroxide killer			
Peroxide Killer	0.20%	0.505 Kg	
Enzyme Treatment			
Acid	1%	2.526 Kg	pH Check
Enzyme	0.05%	0.210 Kg	
BATH DROP after 40 min. of Enzyme treatment			
Dyeing			
Levelling Agent	0.80%	2.020 Kg	pH Check
Remazol Yellow RR	0.004480%	0.018861 Kg	
Remazol Red RR	0.000627%	0.002641 Kg	
Remazol Blue RR	0.000784%	0.003301 Kg	
Glauber Salt	20%	50.520 Kg	
Soda Ash	8%	20.208 Kg	

Table 3.5: Dyeing and Recipe Process

Figure 3.4: BD Card in Dyeing Process

3.12 Common Dyeing Faults with their Remedies

1. Uneven Dyeing Causes:

- Uneven pretreatment (uneven scouring & bleaching)
- Improper color dosing
- Using dyes of high fixation property
- Uneven heat-setting in case of synthetic fibres
- Lack of control on dyeing m/c

Remedies:

- By ensuring even pretreatment
- By ensuring even heat-setting in case of synthetic fibres
- Proper dosing of dyes and chemicals
- Proper controlling of dyeing m/c

2. Batch to Batch Shade Variation Causes:

- Fluctuation of Temperature
- Improper dosing time of dyes & chemicals
- Batch to batch weight variation of dyes and chemicals
- Dyes lot variation
- Improper reel speed, pump speed, liquor ratio
- Improper pretreatment

Remedies:

- Use standard dyes and chemicals
- Maintain the same liquor ration
- Follow the standard pretreatment procedure
- Maintain the same dyeing cycle
- Identical dyeing procedure should be followed for the same depth of the shade

4. Patchy Dyeing Effect:

- Entanglement of fabric
- Faulty injection of alkali
- Improper addition of color
- Due to hardness of water

Remedies:

- By ensuring proper pretreatment
- Proper dosing of dyes and chemicals
- Heat should be same throughout the dye liquor
- Proper salt addition

4. Roll to Roll Variation or Meter to Meter Variation:

- Poor migration property of dyes
- Improper dyes solubility
- Hardness of water
- Faulty m/c speed, etc.

Remedies:

- Use standard dyes and chemicals
- Proper m/c speed

5. Crease Mark:

- Poor opening of the fabric rope
- Shock cooling of synthetic material
- If pump pressure & reel speed is not equal
- Due to high-speed m/c running

Remedies:

- Maintaining proper reel speed & pump speed
- Lower rate rising and cooling the temperature
- Reducing the m/c load
- Higher liquor ration

6. Dye Spots:

- Improper dissolving of dye particle in bath
- Improper dissolving of caustic soda particle in bath

Remedies:

- By proper dissolving of dyes & chemicals

CHAPTER 4: FINISHING

4.1 Introduction to Finishing:

Textile finishing, in a restricted sense, is the term used for a series of processes to which all bleached, dyed, printed and certain grey fabrics are subjected before they are put on the market. In fact, finishing includes the final treatment of every kind of fabric made from every kind of fiber.

Objectives of Finishing:

- Improving the appearance — Luster, whiteness, etc
- Improving the feel, that depends on the handle of the material and its softness, suppleness, fullness, etc.
- Wearing qualities, none — soiling, anti-crease, anti-shrink, comfort, etc.
- Special properties required for particular uses — water — proofing, flame proofing, etc.
- Covering of the faults in the original cloth.
- Increasing the weight of the cloth.

Types of finishing:

- Chemical finishing:
 - a) Chemical reaction of auxiliaries with fibers.
 - b) Application of the handle modifying products / additives
- Mechanical Finishing:
 - a) Mechanical treatment with machines

4.2 Process Flow Chart of Dyeing Finishing:

Chart 4.1: Flow chart of Dyeing Finishing

4.3 Machineries Used in Finishing Section:

Machine No.	Machine Type	Brand	Origin	Quantity
01	De-Water Machine	Bianco	Italy	1
02	Slitting Machine	Bianco	Italy	1
03	Super Slit A.T	Corino	Italy	1
04	Super Slit A.T	Corino	Italy	1
05	Relax Dryer	Canlar	Italy	1
06	Stenter	Bianco	Italy	1
07	Stenter	LK	Taiwan	1
09	Raising Machine	Lafer	Italy	1
10	Sueding Machine	Lafer	Italy	1

Machine No.	Machine Type	Brand	Origin	Quantity
11	Compactor Machine	FERRARO	Italy	1
12	Compactor Machine	FERRARO	Italy	1

Table

4.4 Machine Description of Finishing Section:

De-watering or Squeezer m/c: De-Watering machine plays an important role in knit finishing section of the knit fabrics. De-watering machine is used for reducing water from the wet fabric. It reduces the water content of the fabric.

Function of De-watering m/c:

- Reduce water content.
- Apply chemicals.
- Apply overfeed.
- Open the fabric from rope form.
- Widthwise stretch the fabric.
- Plait the fabric.

Slitting Machine:

Slitting machine or slitter is an industrial equipment is used for tubular fabric for making it to open form finishing line by machine operator for textile design. Slitting is a special process that is useful for cutting the tubular cloth through cut or laser cut machine direction prior to stenter machine and open width compactor machine. During slitting by slitter machine, it is necessary to be very attentive about the cutting line or else, cloth faults can be occurred there any time.

Functions of Slitting Machines:

- Cutting the tube from fabric into open width.
- Squeeze the fabric.
- Shade lighter by padder pressure.

Stenter Machine:

A machine or apparatus for stretching or stentering fabrics. The purpose of the stenter machine is to bringing the length and width to pre determine dimensions and also for heat setting and it is used for applying finishing chemicals and also shade variation is adjusted. The main function of the stenter is to stretch the fabric widthwise and to recover the uniform width.

Functions of Stenter Machines:

- Heat setting is done by the stenter for lycra fabric, synthetic and blended fabric.
- Width of the fabric is controlled by the stenter.
- Finishing chemical apply on fabric by the stenter.
- Loop of the knit fabric is controlled.
- Moisture of the fabric is controlled by the stenter.
- Spirality controlled by the stenter.
- GSM of the fabric is controlled by stenter.
- Fabric is dried by the stentering process.

Compactor Machine:

Compactor is a textile finishing machine which is designed especially for compacting 100% cotton knitted fabric like jersey, pique, interlock, plush, rib and sinker etc. as well as cotton blended fabric in rope form, changing the loft and dimensional stability of the fabric and presenting it to plaited form. Fitted with two felt compacting units which makes it to obtain top quality fabric, with minimized shrinking nature and a soft fluffy hand.

Functions of compactor Machines:

- GSM control of the knitted fabric. For high GSM, overfeed is increased and fabric width is decreased. For low GSM, overfeed is decreased and fabric width is increased.
- Control shrinkage
- Twisting control
- Increase smoothness of fabric
- Heat setting is done of fabric etc.

Textile Dryer:

Drying is done after de-watering of fabric. In textile finishing unit; dryer uses for dry the knit, woven fabrics and dyed yarn. But the drying process and drying mechanism of yarn and fabrics is different

from one to another. The main functions of a textile dryer are to dry the textile fabrics. Drying is defined as a process where the liquid portion of the solution is evaporated from the fabric.

Special Feature of Dryer:

1. Steam dryer (two chambers).
2. Vibration occur in heating zone.
3. Process air pressure switch present.
4. Maximum temp. Increase up to 1700C.
5. Steam control switch present.
6. Two burners present.
7. Two conveyer belt is present.

4.5 Some Figures of Finishing Machineries:

Figure 4.1: Finishing Section

Figure 4.2: Stenter Machine

Figure 4.3: Compactor Machine

4.6 Quality Assurance System:

Quality means customer needs is to be satisfied. Failure to maintain an adequate quality standard can therefore be unsuccessful. But maintaining an adequate standard of quality also costs effort. From the first investigation to find out what the potential customer for a new product really wants, through the processes of design, specification, controlled manufacture and sale.

Quality Parameters of Knitted Fabrics:

There are some quality parameters of knitted fabric. Such as-

- Strength and extensibility.
- Course density.
- Wales's density.
- Lop length.
- Elasticity.
- Deformation.
- Grams per square meter (G.S.M)
- Yarn count.
- Design.

Faults Checking at Quality Inspection: The following faults are found at the time of quality checking after finishing.

- | | |
|-----------------|---------------|
| ➤ Color Spot | ➤ Oil Spot |
| ➤ Softener Spot | ➤ Yellow Spot |
| ➤ Insect Spot | ➤ Joint |
| ➤ Fly Yarn | ➤ Dirt Stain |
| ➤ Patta | ➤ Crease Mark |
| ➤ Hole | ➤ Poly Conta |
| ➤ Needle Mark | |
| ➤ Miss Print | |

CHAPTER 5: CUTTING SECTION

5.1 Cutting

Fabric is cut from the lay and spreading with accuracy and properly which is termed as fabric cutting. It is basically the process by which different garments parts are cut out from the fabric layer with the help of a marker and a cutting machine.

Figure 5.1: Cutting Section

5.2 Precautions Taken

- Proper maintenance of machineries
- Metal hand gloves and using mask
- Careful manual cutting by straight knife
- Proper quality check (spreading) and inspection

5.3 Layout of cutting section

Figure 5.2: Layout of Cutting Section

5.4 Requirements for Cutting

- The weight of the fabric
- Proper relaxation of the fabric
- Width of the fabric
- Number of lays and plies
- Efficient marker and cut order plan
- Manual laying for the fabrics like stripe and check
- Proper fabric spreading
- Proper size and style ticketing or numbering

5.5 Records Kept

- Cut Order Plan
- Marker Length
- No. of Garments
- Garment Quality
- Daily Cutting Report
- Defects Found etc

5.6 Process Flowchart of Cutting Section

Chart 5.1: Flow chart of Cutting Section

5.7 Spreading

Fabric spreading means the smooth laying out of the fabric in superimposed layers (plies) of a specified length.

There are one methods of fabric spreading in HAMS Group -

- Completely manual laying-up

There are few requirements for fabric spreading:

- Alignment of fabric plies
- Optimum ply tension
- Flat appearance of the fabric is required
- Elimination of fabric with flaws or defects
- Correct ply direction and stability (all faces up/all faces down/face to face)
- Easy separation of the cut lay into bundles
- Avoidance of fusing of plies during cutting (using anti-fuse paper between plies)
- Avoidance of distortion in spreading
- Matching the checks and stripes etc.

Before spreading, some points should be checked-

- Shade approves
- GSM & Shrinkage test report
- Style-wise pattern & marker

Figure 5.3: Fabric Spreading

5.8 Lay height

Lay height depends on fabric type by maintaining (Standard lay height chart)

Fabric Type	Lay height	No of ply max
100% cotton fleece	4"	50
Lycra/terry fleece	3"	50
Cotton Pique	3"	80
100% cotton single jersey	3"	100
100% cotton rib	3"	60
Lycra pique	2.5"	60
Interlock	2.5"	60
Lycra/Viscose/Polyester Mix	2	60

Table 5.1: Standard lay height chart

Figure 5.4: Numbering & Block Checking

Marker efficiency normally: 85-87 %

But marker efficiency in this project: 83.65%

5.9 Factors which influence the Marker Efficiency

- Manufacturers of the marker;
- Size of pattern pieces;
- Length of the marker;
- Pattern Engineering;
- Nature of the fabric;
- Method of marker making;
- Marker width;
- Kinds or design of garments.

5.10 Block check

- Pattern check
- Miscut
- Cut mark/ Notches
- Machine placement
- Rigged

Note:

They use wastage fabric to attached bundle card stickers to identify block panels easily.

5.11 Cutting process description

Fabric: The cutting room in charge requests fabric from the fabric store based on the daily cutting plan made by the cutting room executive. The fabric is requested using Fabric Requisition Slip format. The cutting room helper gets the fabric from the stores & transfers it to cutting room with the help of fabric movement trolley. The fabric received is stored in the fabric racks within the cutting-room.

Fabric Relaxation: The fabric received in the roll form should be relaxed for at least 12 hours under standard conditions before spreading. This is done in order to take out any tension in the fabric imparted during finishing or winding so as to avoid any distortion while spreading or cutting.

Spreading & Marking: Before Spreading, the lay plan should be prepared & a lay order slip is generated by cutting executive. The lay order slip provides all relevant details to the spreader for the lay i.e. style, fabric width, no. of plies, marker way, consumption for that lay etc. The spreader has to follow the lay-order slip for considerations during spreading & if he finds any deviations in the actual, it should be reported to the cutting executive. After the spreading is done, the lay should be checked by the QC and a format called Cutting Room Inspection Report is generated. After the lay is cleared by the QC, it goes for next operation i.e. marking. The marking could be done manually by patterns or paper marker could be fixed on top ply to make it ready.

Numbering & Bundling: Once the lay is cut the cut parts are numbered, all parts that makes one complete garment is given same number so as to avoid any mismatching of shade. After numbering

the pieces are bundled into a group of certain pieces. The size of the bundle is decided by the cutting-room in charge, in discussion with the sewing floor in charge.

Quality Audit: All bundles need to be audited for quality before issuing to the sewing lines. Quality audit on the bundled garments is done by the cutting-room auditor who checks the bundles for bundle ticket descriptions, correct sequence of ply numbers, presence of all parts etc. mentioned in the format. The shade matching, notch positioning, etc. These audits are conducted following the AQL chart specifications & a format called Cutting Section Bundle Audit is filled.

6.3 Types of print used in HAMS Fashion Ltd

1. Screen Printing
2. Rubber Printing
3. High density Print
4. Sticker Print
5. Heat Print
6. Foil print
7. Flock Print
8. Glitter Print
9. Metallic Print

6.4 Chemical needed for printing

1. Dyes
2. Binder
3. Softener
4. Thickener
5. Fixer
6. Clear
7. Water
8. Resin
9. Metal Powder

6.5 Color Paste Preparation

When printing textiles, the dye or pigment is not in aqueous liquor, instead, it is usually finely dispersed in a printing paste, in high concentration. Here the color is made according to the requirements of the buyer by following the code of Pantone number.

6.6 Screen Preparation Flowchart

Chart 6.1: Flow chart of Screen Preparation

6.7 Printing paste preparation

6.7.1 Pigment Printing Paste

- BR 1000 (Binder +Thickener)
- Pigment
- Fixing agent (Only for Acid wash, Enzyme wash)

6.7.2 Rubber printing paste

- White 101 for white rubber
- Clear 594 for color rubber
- MK binder

6.7.3 Flock Print

- Sheet flock
- Powder flock

6.7.4 Glitter print

- Glitter comical (100 %) + glitter (10%) + fixer (5%)

6.7.5 Foil Print

- Foil gum – hit phrase gold or other color

6.7.6 Crack print:

- Chemical 2 types
- Crack clear
- Crack white Hand fell:
- Layer
- No gloss
- Hard

6.8 Defects of Printing

- Flushing/Wicking: Caused due to Low viscosity of impress paste. It occurs when the printed expanse bleeds out into the unprinted area. The resultant is a haloing or shadowing outcome or thence the outline of the pattern design.
- Bleeding: Caused due to Low viscosity of impress glue. It is major defect every bit it happens throughout the stuff unless the viscosity is corrected.
- Misfits: A misfit is an impress defect caused yesteryear improper alignment of the screens. Also known every bit out of registration, misfits teach out unprinted areas inwards the design.
- Scrimps: A scrimp defect occurs when the stuff creases underneath 1 of the screens during the printing process. The pattern is thence printed on plow over of the crease, leaving a large unprinted expanse when the stuff returns to its relaxed state.
- Banding: Defect created yesteryear the impress head's motility over the substrate. Use of scanning impress head, or an impress caput that moves dorsum as well as forth across the substrate inwards lead trouble placing drops of ink at precise locations along the line.

- Unwanted paint marker on Fabric: Caused due to concealment has holes inwards it that should accept been covered. This could locomote because of ageing of the concealment as well as eventual harm or but improper exposure to light
- Crack or Miss Alignment inwards Transfer Printed Fabric: Incomplete transfer of blueprint from newspaper to stuff on transfer printing due to removal of transfer of newspaper land the stuff was notwithstanding hot.
- Color out: The resultant of color running depression inwards reservoir on printing machine

CHAPTER 7: GARMENTS SECTION

7.1 Garments

Garments are the final achievement of textile processing, which started from fiber as a raw material of finished goods. After completing spinning, weaving, wet processing; the materials are ready for apparel manufacturing. Apparel is made generally from dyed or printed fabrics. The process of making a garment according to the pattern, desired design and style is called garment manufacturing.

7.2 Machineries Used in Garments Section

Sl. No	Machine Type	Brand Name	Origin
1	Rib Cutting M/C	Juki	India
2	Over lock M/C	Juki	India
3	Flat lock M/C	Juki	India
4	Plain M/C	Juki	India
5	Button- Eyelet Hole/Attaching M/C	Juki	India
6	Bar tack M/C	Juki	India
7	Smocking M/C	Juki	India
8	Kansain M/C	Juki	India
9	Zig-Zug M/C	juki	India
10	Ironing M/C	Juki	India
11	Metal Detector M/C	Morgan	Italy
12	Pocket Attaching & Sewing M/c	Juki	India
13	Auto cutting M/c	Morgan, JOKER	Italy
14	Auto cutting M/c	Lectra, NEXT-90	France
15	Straight Knife	BRUTE	Japan

Table 7.1: Machineries Used in Garment Section

7.3 General Flow Chart of Garment Manufacturing

Chart 7.1: Flow chart of Garment Manufacturing

7.4 Sample Section in Garment Industry

Garment sample section is very important department in apparel manufacturing process. Garmentsamples are inevitably important and are developed tested before starting the bulk production, because the buyers generally place the order after they are satisfied with the quality of the samples. The samples decide the ability of an exporter. If the samples are of good quality and with reasonable price naturally the buyers will be forced to place the order.

The details attached with the garments sample:

- Reference No. / Style No.
- Color
- Fabric Composition
- Wash Type
- Size
- Trims & Accessories details
- Quality
- Sample type
- Description etc.

Objective of Garment Sample Making:

- To allow the buyer to judge the production capabilities of the manufacturer.
- To provide a means for making revisions in the bulk production process.
- To let the manufacturer, estimate the thread and fabric consumption, and develop cost quotations

Flow Chart of Sample Make

Chart 7.2: Flow chart of Sample Making

Types of Sample Mark

Different types of samples make according to different buyer. It depends on Buyer demands. Like-

- Proto Sample
- Fit sample
- Sales man sample
- Size-set sample
- Pre-Production sample
- Top of production sample
- Shipment sample
- Counter sample etc.

7.5 Sewing Section

After receive the garments components from cutting section, all the garments' parts are joined and sewn as sequentially. Obviously, all the components are sewn respects on buyer requirement. Sewing section is the most important department of a garment manufacturing industry. Sewing machines of different types are arranged as a vertical line to assemble the garments. Sequence of types of sewing machine arrangement depends on sequence of assembling operations. Sewing section of this garment is divided into ten units. Total area of this section is about 55,000 square feet. There are a total of 88 functional sewing lines in the factory.

Figure 7.1: Sewing Section

7.6 Standard Minute Value (SMV):

SMV is defined as the time which is allowed to perform a job satisfactorily. Normally it is expressed in minute value. The full elaboration of SMV is Standard Minute Value. SMV term is broadly used in the garments manufacturing industry. SMV is also known as Standard Allocated Minute (SAM)

SMV = (Basic minute + Bundle allowance + Machine and Personal allowance)

Sewing of Basic T-Shirt:

1. **Over lock M/C:** Shoulder Join, Neck Join, Sleeve Join, Side Seam
2. **Flat Lock M/C:** Sleeve Hem, Body hem, Neck top stitch
3. **Plain M/C:** Back neck top, Label attach, Neck tuck, Rib tuck.

7.7 Calculation of Garments Production

There are some points which must be needed during calculation of garments production, those are-

- Standard allowed minutes (SAM),
- Number of operators- working in a line,
- Number of hours running-production line work in a day,
- Average line efficiency,
- Total break time including Launch, Tea and Others.

During calculation of garments production, we have to follow a formula, that is-

Per Day Production:

$$PC = \frac{\text{Total man-minutes needed in a day}}{\text{Standard allowed minutes}} * \text{Average line efficiency} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Here, total man-minutes mean number of operators working in a day including total break time for Launch, Tea and Others.

CHAPTER 8: PRODUCTION PLANNING & CONTROL

8.1 Production Planning

For efficient, effective and economical operation in a manufacturing unit of an organization, it is essential to integrate the production planning and control system. Production planning and subsequent production control follow adaptation of product design and finalization of a production process.

Production planning is one part of production planning and control dealing with basic concepts of what to produce, when to produce, how much to produce, etc. It involves taking a long-term view at overall production planning. A Production Planning to Maintain the Production Capacity and the Resources.

Therefore, objectives of production planning are as follows:

- To ensure right quantity and quality of raw material, equipment, etc. are available during times of production.
- To ensure capacity utilization is in tune with forecast demand at all the time.

A well thought production planning ensures that overall production process is streamlined providing following benefits:

- Organization can deliver a product in a timely and regular manner.
- Suppliers are informed will in advance for the requirement of raw materials.
- It reduces investment in inventory.
- It reduces overall production cost by driving in efficiency.

8.2 Production Control

Production control looks to utilize different type of control techniques to achieve optimum performance out of the production system as to achieve overall production planning targets.

Therefore, objectives of production control are as follows:

- Regulate inventory management
- Organize the production schedules

- Optimum utilization of resources and production process

The advantages of robust production control are as follows:

- Ensure a smooth flow of all production processes
- Ensure production cost savings thereby improving the bottom line
- Control wastage of resources
- It maintains standard of quality through the production life cycle.

8.3 Production & planning system

Planning gives a scheduled task and control completes it successfully. But production planning and control is not an easy task. Its basic working procedure is as follows-

- Taking order from marketing division
- Analyzing the orders.
- Planning for knitting the fabric
- Planning for dyeing the fabric
- Planning for finishing the fabric

It is only a basic procedure. It may change according to the type of order. Sometimes the order is placed only for finishing the materials or only for dyeing the goods. Then some steps are minimizing for planning.

Taking order from marketing division:

Marketing division supplied fabric orders to the planning and control division by a specific format.

Analyzing the orders:

After getting the fabric order, this section analyzes the orders according to buyers order quantity, type of orders (i.e. type of fabric, color to be dyed etc.), delivery date etc. This section plans for required quantity of fabric to be knitted (order quantity + 10% of the order quantity), knitting balance, fabric to be dyed, dyeing balance, RFD (ready for delivery), RFD balance, delivery fabric & delivery balance etc.

Planning for knitting:

This section plans for knitting production. It selects m/c for knitting the fabric, no of m/c to be used, type of yarn used, from which source yarn will be collected, required GSM width etc. It also gives delivery date of knitted fabric.

Planning for dyeing the fabric:

Production planning for dyeing is called “Batch plan”. Batch plan is prepared according to the batch no, fabric construction, color, width, GSM and priority of delivery etc and written in a batch card.

Planning for finishing the fabric:

Finishing schedule are same as the dyeing. After dyeing, materials go to the finishing section with the batch plan. Finishing data is written to the batch card and is informed to the planning section. However, this section always forces to all the departments to finish all the work within the delivery time given by the buyers. Thus, it plays a very important role in the success of the company.

8.4 Quality control:

Quality Control Circles at Workplace to Maintain the Quality of our Works from all the Sides. In NTL Japan based TQM is followed to maintain the Maximum Quality of our Products.

Quality Policy – A planned and continuously updated quality policy for respected buyers to maintain the maximum quality of products at any cost.

Quality Vision – NTL has set a vision for our quality management by the named Vision 2020 (Quality). By this time period we are committed to be best one arena of Quality in Textile Manufacturing.

Quality Team – Developed and maintained a skilled and experienced Quality Team to implement quality policy and to ensure the quality of NTL products.

Quality Control Circles – It developed 18 Quality Control Circles at factory who are working dedicatedly (self) for the workplace problem solving which problems could be hampered the quality of our products.

Training and Development - Different types of Training, Seminar and Workshop on Quality Improvement for personnel of quality department regularly.

Quality Checking and Maintenance:

- Total goods are checked before shipment for quality assurance.
- Yarns are lab-tested for pilling resistance, color fastness etc.
- All kinds of raw materials are preserved in warehouses in a professional manner.
- Production only starts after their approval & also prior approval on quality.
- All production floors keep clean and maintain all necessary safety measures according to compliance

To fulfill the vision 2020 NTL has to become the market leader according to the quality products for its customers. As a result, its Quality Team is Skilled and Experienced. Proper and update quality working procedure to assure the quality of its products.

8.5 Costing of the Product

Costing system mainly describe how the cost of the final product is fixed by the company or top managements. As it is a garments manufacturing factory, so according to the buyer or customer requirements of final garments, merchandiser give the consumption of the fabric with specifications. Then it is calculated how much dyestuffs & chemicals are required for processing. After that, the final cost is fixed including some profit. Then the unit price is offered to the buyer for their approval.

Costing of a Product Includes

- Yarn cost
- Knitting cost
- Dyes and chemicals cost
- Cost of dyeing
- Cost of finishing
- Cost of cutting, sewing, accessories etc.
- Cost of printing (If any)

- Labor cost (direct & indirect)
- Factory cost
- Office & administrative cost
- Sales and caring cost
- Others cost
- Profit etc.

CHAPTER 9: MERCHANDISING ACTIVITIES

9.1 DATA COLLECTION

Collection of facts (raw facts) is known as data. Direct observation and personal interview with questionnaire are the main instrument to collect the data. Primary data have been used for the purpose of the study. The primary data have been collected on the basics of prepared questionnaire. I collect lots of data which is related to my study topic technical merchandising in Apparel industry. This collected data are given below:

Normally there are two types of invoices:

1. preform invoice: it is needed at primary stage of any order for opening L/C.
2. Commercial Invoice: it is needed at final stage of any order for asking payment from buyer.

A merchandiser always should have a mentality to impress the buyers by means of:

- Right Product.
- Right Qualities.
- Right Quantities.
- Right Time.

9.2 Samples always should be sent with below information on tag

- a) Date
- b) Style
- c) Color
- d) Size
- e) Full description of garment
- f) Fabric description (content, construction, weight etc)
- g) Name of customer
- h) Name of vendor
- i) Unit price (if needed)
- j) Any sample sent to buyer must be the good one in terms

Woven fabric three types. Such as,

- I. Yarn dyed
- II. Solid dyed
- III. Printed.

9.3 Application of the P.O. Sheet in the Factory

From the previous discussion, this is much clarified that the Purchase Order Sheet is how much essential for beginning the production of a particular order to be purchased. Way of Application:

- When an exporter or a buyer confirms a merchandise to purchase, he sends a Purchase Order Sheet to the assigned merchandiser.
- After receiving the P.O. sheet, it has to be sent in each department of the factory related to the purchasing from getting order to the shipment of the merchandise.

Therefore, the P.O. sheets are copied a few copies –

- a) For cutting section,
- b) For commercial section,
- c) For each production floor,
- d) For the merchandiser himself,
- e) For others if needed.

9.4 Preparation of production files for production starting

- Measurement sheet
- Assortment
- Fabric quantity
- Approval Sample
- Order sheet
- Packing list
- Carton measurement.

9.5 Calculation of button ligne from mm (millimeter)

If Button length (dia) is 12.7 mm then Button ligne will be ?

Rule:

Button dia (in mm) / 0.635 = button ligne

12.7 mm / 0.635 = 20 L (L = ligne)

Result = 20 L

9.5.1 Chart of button ligne (mm to ligne)

Figure 9.1: Chart of button ligne

9.6 Pricing Terminologies used in Garment Exports

Free on Board (FOB): In garment exporting, pricing of the garments mostly quoted on FOB.

FOB is defined as a term of sale under which the price invoiced or quoted by an exporter manufacturer or a buying agency includes all charges up to placing the goods on board a ship at the port of departure specified by the buyer.

9.7 Calculation of fabric consumption for knits garment

Like other business, garment factory is set for profit generation. Profit can be improved by saving from each cost factors of garment making. Fabric is most important constitute of garment and it represent around 60-70% of total product manufacturing cost. Fabric cost of a product depends how much fabric is consumed to make the garment including cut wastes and end bits.

CHAPTER 10: COMPLIANCE SECTION

10.1 Human resource management

Human resource management is the process of hiring and developing employees so that they become more valuable to the organization.

Human Resource Management includes conducting job analysis, planning personnel needs, recruiting the right people for the job, orienting and training, managing wages and salaries, providing benefits and incentives evaluating performance, resolving disputes, and communicating with all employees at all levels. Examples of core qualities of HR management are extensive knowledge of the industry, leadership, and effective negotiation skills.

10.2 Administration department

An administration department is responsible for providing administrative aid in five areas of a business: information management systems, human resources, payroll, acquisition and communication. The goal of the administration department is to keep all departments within a business operating at maximum capacity. The administrative offices associated with a garments manufacturing facility are typically proportional to the size of the manufacturing operation.

10.3 Flow chart of administration department

Chart 10.1: Flow chart of administration

10.4 Compliance of HAMS Group

- Compensation for holiday
- Leave with wages
- Health register
- Time care
- Accident register
- Workman register
- Equal remuneration
- National festival holiday
- Overtime register
- Labor welfare
- Weekly holiday fund
- Sexual harassment policy
- Child labor abolition policy
- Anti-discrimination policy
- Zero abasement policy

10.5 Health Safety

HAMS Group give proper health safety for employees. They Provide –

- Cup availability
- Drinking water supply
- Water cooler, heater available in canteen
- Drinking water vassal clean at once in a week
- Water reserve at least once a week

10.6 Fire Safety

- Sufficient fire extinguisher and active
- Access area without hindrance

CHAPTER 11: MAINTENANCE

11.1 Maintenance of Machinery

The machineries used in textile wet processing should be subjected to scheduled maintenance Activities for their optimum performances at their following points:

- Routes of different utilities like water, steam, gas, electricity, compressed air, etc.
- Dyestuff & chemical dosing system.
- Drainage system of waste water, color & chemical.
- Driving arrangement of different machineries.
- Power transmission to different machineries.
- Fabric guiding system through the machineries.
- Cleanliness of machine parts.

11.2 Maintenance Schedule:

- Perform visual inspection
- Check bearing.
- Clean & grease.
- Inspecting all sides.
- Clean & oiling.
- Cleaning of drain valves
- Checking of all electrical wires.
- Checking of circuit breaker, magnetic contractors.

11.3 Maintenance Tools & Their Equipment

The most important maintenance tools that are used frequently are tabulated

Maintenance Tools	Function
Grease	Lubrication
Tread tape	Joining of broken metallic parts
Cutting disk	For cutting pipes, rods
Glove valve	Fitting from stem line

Maintenance Tools	Function
Union	Fittings of water, steam line
Union elbow	Fittings of water, steam line
Cutting oil	Lubrication
Gear oil	Lubrication
Hydraulic oil	Lubrication
Oil gun	Oil application
Spanner	Tightening of nut bolts
Master range	Tightening of nut bolts
Flat screwdriver	Screw tightening & loosening
Star screwdriver	Screw tightening & loosening
Hacksaw blade	Cutting
Hacksaw frame	Cutting
Spray gun WP40	Spraying a chemical named WP40 that lubricates bearings.
Drill machine	Drilling to make holes
Grinding machine	Grinding

Table 11.1: Function of Maintenance Tools

11.4 Boiler Machine Maintenance Schedule

- Daily:**
- Check gas pressure
 - Maintain log sheet
 - Chemical dosing
- Weekly:**
- Check all steam line
 - Fire quality of boiler
- Monthly:**
- Check all steam line
 - Fire quality of boiler
 - Gas consumption report
 - Burner clean

- Quarterly:**
- Burner clean
 - Economizer clean
 - Feed tank clean
 - Chemical tank clean
 - Sight glass clean
- Half yearly:**
- Burner clean
 - Feed tank clean
 - Chemical tank clean
 - Economizer clean
 - Replace gasket
 - Replace valve
 - Check gas line & filter & pressure
- Yearly:**
- Overhauling of boiler
 - Chemical cleaning of boiler
 - Safety valve test
 - Economizer clean
 - Feed tank clean
 - Chemical tank clean
 - Burner clean
 - Check safety valve setting
 - Replace valve & gasket

11.5 Remarks: As maximum machines are new, so they need a few maintenances that is the breakdown maintenance.

CHAPTER 12: CONCLUSION

HAMS Group is a well-known knit composite textile industry in Bangladesh since 1994. I am very proud to take my industrial training in such a leading industry.

To speak the truth, it's the Industrial Training which visualizes my four years academic course in 2 months only. It helps me to understand the complicated steps of knitting, sewing, merchandising, and the difficult topics of Textile which we just learned by heart in our academic session in the department. So, I thank HAMS Group for the knowledge I gathered from this training will be an asset for my future life.

HAMS Group has an ethical industrial culture in most points of view. The employees are helpful to each other as well as to the trainees. I have got immense support from all the members of HAMS Group & expect its onward development.